

Site: Sphinx Temple Season '80

Area: N. Colonnade Square R16 Locus Number (2) LEVEL 1

Progress of Excavation ENTIRE AREA CLEANED + then level 1
ca. .5-16.0 cm below cleaned SURFACE REMOVED. Pits with
modern Rubbish, sand pit, mud deposit + fallen +
DECAYED STONE ENCOUNTERED. Soil REMOVED SCREENED
AND Shards, STONE etc. REMOVED. NO Float samples or
soil samples collected. Bottom of Level PLANED.
No Photo taken. EXCAVATED with Trowel + BRUSH.

Locus Description Pit of SAND at NORTH end through which camel thorn
roots grew fallen stone + MUD Brick to N.E. STRAUM of
mud (dk. BROWN soil) containing stone (granite + LIME.) chips and FLECKS
of charcoal RUNNING through cta. of TRENCH. DECAYED limestone also in fill.

Location in Square TO WEST of FALLEN core block RUNNING
FROM exposed PAVEMENT TO wall with sub-balk at base
of block.

Under Locus _____ Over Locus _____

Locus Dimensions 2.70 m. x 1.00 m

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____